

OPTIMIZING HEALTH CARE: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON PREVENTION PRACTICES IN NOSOCOMIAL INFECTION IN SELECTED HOSPITALS

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the prevention practices among healthcare workers in different hospitals in Eastern Pangasinan. It tackled their age, gender preference, civil status, highest educational attainment, professional area, number of years in service, area of assignment, employment status, and hospital facility. The study utilized the descriptive research design and a survey questionnaire as the main tools for gathering data. Several statistical tools were used, such as frequency and percentage, weighted mean, t-test, Scheffe test, and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance). The healthcare worker respondents were mainly young adults, women, singles, and bachelor's degree holders; most were nurses in the service for more than five years, primarily assigned to OPD/ER, regular employees. The preventive practices among healthcare workers are the highest regarding personal hand hygiene and protective equipment. The gender preference of the health workers affects their preventive practices to control nosocomial infections, while environmental preventive practices do not affect the healthcare workers to prevent nosocomial infections. Women healthcare workers are more meticulous in rendering their nursing care compared to the males, and the area of assignment of the health workers significantly affects their preventive practices to control nosocomial infections. The main ways to protect a patient from infections from other patients and healthcare providers are through aseptic technique, personal protective equipment and environmental infection control measures. Furthermore, the proposed effective measures for mitigating the risk of healthcare-related infections, namely sterilization of equipment, waste segregation, provision of adequate PPEs, sanitizers, and antiseptics, hospital ventilation, clean environment and hand hygiene.

INTRODUCTION

Nosocomial infections commonly occur in hospitals. The patients who are admitted are most commonly affected. Patients and healthcare professionals bring microbes inside the hospitals, and they pass them on to other people. Individuals carry these germs without being sick, and they spread them to others without knowing. The immune system becomes weak to fight the microbes. To be considered nosocomial, the infection must not be present at admission but must develop at least 48 hours after admission. These infections can lead to severe problems like sepsis and even death Cheung, J. (2023). When sick, the body's immune system goes down, making the patient vulnerable to the infection. Microbes are transferred to persons by merely handling surfaces like doorknobs and other tools used for the patient. These illnesses can be encountered in both private and public hospitals. When these infections occur while in the hospital, they lead to more extended hospital stays and illness. While in the hospital, patients are exposed to illnesses from various sources, including medical professionals and other sick patients.

Microorganisms can be transmitted during coughing, sneezing, talking, and suctioning and are expelled before settling onto a surface. It causes the infection to be deposited directly into a susceptible person's body or environmental surfaces and then touched by a susceptible person. Contact transmission is the most crucial and frequent mode of communication in health care. Organisms are transferred through direct contact between an infected and a susceptible healthcare worker or another person. Patient organisms can be transferred to the intact skin of a healthcare worker and then transferred to a susceptible patient who develops an infection. An infected patient touching a doorknob, then touched by health care workers and transferred to another patient (Collins, 2023). It clearly states that infections can enter the body quickly through different mediums.

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), hand hygiene is the single most important practice in the prevention of transmission of infection in the healthcare setting. Studies showed that hygiene's importance must be adequately recognized amongst healthcare professionals, and compliance needs to be higher. Contaminated hands of healthcare providers are a primary source of microbial spread. Proper hand hygiene decreases the growth of microorganisms, reducing infection risk and length of hospital stay (Butler et al., 2023). Hand hygiene is the simplest method to prevent microbes from entering the body. The wards must have adequate water supply to cleanse spoiled hands.

Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) is a barrier between infectious materials and the skin, mouth, nose, or eyes. The barrier blocks the transmission of contaminants from blood, body fluids, or respiratory secretions. PPE protects patients from contracting infections through a surgical procedure, a medical condition, or exposure to substances

or infectious material brought in by visitors and healthcare workers. When used correctly and with other infection control practices such as hand-washing, using alcohol-based hand sanitizers, and covering coughs and sneezes, it minimizes the spread of infection from one person to another. Effective use of PPE includes appropriately removing and disposing of contaminated PPE to prevent exposing both health workers and other people to infection (FDA, 2020). PPE provides a barrier to minimizing workplace hazards that healthcare providers encounter from harmful exposures. Contamination threats are encountered throughout healthcare (Kening & Groen, 2023). PPE is specialized equipment used to provide a barrier between individuals and microorganisms. This barrier reduces the likelihood of touching or transmitting pathogens. Keep everyone safe from illness.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) (2018), 85% of healthcare waste is solid from used medical supplies, packaging, cleaning products, and food waste. All waste has the potential to contaminate groundwater supplies and pollute the environment with pathogens and toxins. According to the International Council for Nurses, the nursing profession world-wide recognizes the vital role the natural environment plays in global health and acknowledges the real threat posed by medical waste. Aside from using sanitizers and PPEs, the nurse also ensures that the wastes are properly disposed of in color-coded trash bins, depending on the waste category. Nurses in clinical care are producers of medical waste and are active participants in waste disposal procedures. They are also involved in developing policies that deal with the procurement of supplies as well as the production and elimination of medical waste.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework:

This study utilized the Change Theory of Nursing developed by Kurt Lewin. He theorized a three-stage model of change known as the unfreezing-change-refreeze model that requires prior learning to be rejected and replaced. The Change Theory has three major concepts: driving forces, restraining forces, and equilibrium. Driving forces push in a direction that causes change to occur. They facilitate change because they move the patient in the desired direction. They cause a shift in equilibrium toward change. Restraining forces are those forces that counter the driving forces. They hinder change because they push the patient in the opposite direction. They cause a shift in equilibrium that opposes change. Equilibrium is a state of being where driving forces equal restraining forces and no change occurs. Changes between the driving and restraining forces can raise or lower it.

This theory has been adapted because changes must be made to prevent infections while the patient is admitted to the hospital.

This study focused on the comprehensive research of preventive practices to control nosocomial infection among healthcare workers in selected hospitals in Pangasinan. Box number 1 is the input that dealt with the respondents' profile and the preventive practices among healthcare workers. Box number 2 is the process focused on the data gathering, interpretation, and analysis of findings, and Box number 3 is the

output, which deals with the proposed preventive measures for mitigating the risk of healthcare-related infection.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the study

Research Questions

In this context, the researcher is interested in conducting the study to determine nurses' preventive practices to prevent the occurrence of nosocomial infections in hospitals and to share preventive strategies that could assist and improve healthcare professionals' knowledge.

This study determined the preventive practices to control nosocomial infection among selected hospitals in Pangasinan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of their;
 - a. age;
 - b. gender;
 - c. civil status;
 - d. highest educational attainment;
 - e. professional area;
 - f. number of years in service;
 - g. employment status;
 - h. area of assignment; and
 - i. type of facility?
2. What are the preventive practices performed by healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections?
 - a. Personal
 - a1. Hand hygiene, and
 - a2. personal protective equipment
 - b. Environmental
 - b1. Hospital ventilation,
 - b2. Sterilization equipment and patients' area room,
 - b3. Water sanitation, and
 - b4. Waste segregation?
3. Is there significant relationships between the preventive practices perform by healthcare workers to control nosocomial infection across their profile variables?
4. Is there significant difference between the preventive practices perform by healthcare workers to control nosocomial infection across their profile variables?
5. Based on the findings, what proposed effective measures for mitigating the risk of healthcare related infections?

Null Hypothesis

The study was tested in its null form at the 0.05 level of significance, that is,

1. There is no significant relationship between the preventive practices performed by healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections across their profile variables.
2. There is no significant difference between the preventive practices performed by profile variables.

METHODOLOGY

The research approach is presented in this chapter and includes discussions on the research design, subjects of the study, sampling scheme, data gathering instruments, data gathering procedures, statistical treatment of data, and tools for data analysis.

Research Design

The research utilized the descriptive approach, applying the questionnaire as a data gathering tool to determine the preventive practices of health care workers in nosocomial infections in selected hospitals. According to Best (2015); descriptive research is a process that goes beyond the mere gathering together with data tabulation. Interpreting the importance and meaning of the described material is a necessary component. Thus, description is often combined with comparison and contrast involving measurements, classifications, interpretation, and evaluation.

Population and Locale of the Study

The study's respondents were healthcare workers in selected hospitals in Pangasinan who are currently employed in health facilities. They are nurses, medical doctors, midwives, medical lab workers, and rehabilitation workers. To represent the population, purposive sampling was used and was delimited to the healthcare workers assigned to the different areas of the hospital.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized a survey questionnaire based on previous studies and articles related to the study, particularly Butler et al. (2023). Part I focused on the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender preference, civil status, highest educational attainment, professional area, number of years in service, employment status, and type of hospital facility. Part II dealt with preventive practices among healthcare workers to control nosocomial infection through personal use of PPE and environmental measures such as hospital ventilation, sterilization of equipment, water sanitation, and waste segregation.

Validation of Instrument

To gather information from the respondents, a questionnaire was used. The questions about the nosocomial infection prevention practices in a selected hospitals were taken from a number of academic articles. Nevertheless, experts in the medical and nursing areas, including physicians, nurses, lab technicians, academic researchers, and educators with training in infection control, verified it. The whole rating showed a very high degree of validity.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before gathering data, the researcher secured permission from the Dean of the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies to conduct the study. When permission was granted from the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies, the researcher requested and coordinated with the Chief of Hospitals through the Chief Nurse to collect the necessary data from the specified respondents. When approval is acquired from the

institutional management, the researcher meets with the respondents to determine a suitable schedule for distributing the research instruments. Following that, the researcher assisted the research tools personally in dealing with any doubt or misunderstanding on the part of the respondents as they dealt with the various questions in the instruments.

Treatment of Data

For Problem No. 1 on the respondent's profile, frequency and percentage were used. The frequency was determined based on the number of respondents who answered or checked a particular item on the questionnaire.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{F \times 100}{N}$$

where: P = percentage

F = frequency

N = total number of respondents

For problem No. 2, on the preventive practices in the control of nosocomial infection, the weighted mean was used. A weighted mean is the mean of a set of values, wherein each value or measurement has a different weight or degree of importance. This study used a five-point rating scale system, as shown in the table below.

Formula:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fi}{N}$$

where: \bar{x} = weighted mean

N = total # of population; and

fi = frequencies corresponding to the given items.

<u>Literal Value</u>	<u>Statistical Limit</u>	<u>Descriptive Equivalent</u>	<u>Transmuted Rating</u>
A	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Knowledgeable
B	3.50 – 4.49	Often	Knowledgeable
C	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Knowledgeable
D	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Knowledgeable
E	1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Knowledgeable

For Problems No. 3 and 4 on the significant differences and relationships between the preventive practices to control nosocomial infection, Analysis of Variance was used to test the difference, whereas Chi-Square was used to test the relationship between variables

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

$$F = \frac{MSb}{MSw}$$

Where:

MSb-Mean Square Between

MSw-Mean Square Within

Chi-Square

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where: O =observed number of cases

$$E = \frac{(\text{row total}) (\text{column total})}{\text{Grand total}}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the findings of the study based on the data gathered from the nurse respondents.

Part I. Table 1 presents the characteristics of the respondents, including age, marital status, greatest level of education attained, years of service, work status, and kind of hospital facility.

Age. It can be gleaned from the table that the majority of the respondents are in the age bracket of 31–40 years old with a frequency of 53, or 53 percent, followed by 21–30 years old with a frequency of 36, or 36 percent, 51 and above with a frequency of 5, or 5 percent, and 41–59 years old with a frequency of 5, or 5 percent. It revealed that the respondents were young adults. According to Erikson, 31–40 years old are considered young adults. Young adults need to form intimate, loving relationships with other people. Success leads to strong relationships, while failure results in loneliness and isolation. This stage covers the period of early adulthood when people are exploring personal relationships.

Gender Preference. Most respondents were women, with a frequency of 64 or 64 percent, followed by men, with a frequency of 43 or 34 percent. It showed that most healthcare workers were from the nursing service. It implies that there were more employees in the nursing service as respondents, and nursing is a female-dominated profession.

Civil status. Most of the respondents were single, with a frequency of 62, or 62 percent, followed by married, with a frequency of 35, or 35 percent, and separated, with a frequency of 3, or 3 percent. It revealed that the respondents were not yet into marital relationships and were pursuing their experiences in their field of specialization.

Highest educational attainment. It revealed that the majority of the respondents were bachelor's degree holders, with a frequency of 79, or 79 percent, followed by those with master's units, with a frequency of 10 or 10 percent, master's degree holders, with a frequency of 8, or 8 percent, and doctoral graduates, with a frequency of 8, or 8 percent. It showed that the majority should have pursued a higher level of learning. It is a fact that having a high level of learning will be necessary for professionals.

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents in terms of their Profile Variables

n=100

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)		
21 – 30	36	36.0
31 – 40	53	53.0
41 – 50	5	5.0
51 and above	6	6.0
Gender Preference		
Man	34	34.0
Woman	64	64.0
Transgender	2	2.0
Civil Status		
Single	62	62.0
Married	35	35.0
Separated	3	3.0
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	79	79.0
With Master's units	10	10.0
Master's Degree	8	8.0
Doctoral Degree	3	3.0

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Professional Area		
Medical Doctor	7	7.0
Nurse	66	66.0
Midwife	2	2.0
Nursing Aide	8	8.0
Medical Lab	11	11.0
Dentist	2	2.0
Pharmacist	2	2.0
Radiology	2	2.0
Number of Years in Service		
Below 1 year	24	24.0
1 – 2	19	19.0
3 – 4	17	17.0
5 or more	40	40.0
Area of Assignment		
OPD/ER	38	38.0
Medical	19	19.0
Surgical	7	7.0
OB	7	7.0
ICU	6	6.0
OR	8	8.0
DR	2	2.0
Lab	9	9.0
Ward	2	2.0
Pharmacy	2	2.0
Employment Status		
Job Order	13	13.0
Contractual	15	15.0
Casual	19	19.0
Regular	53	53.0
Type of Facility		
Private	42	42.0
Government	58	58.0

Professional area. It showed that the majority of the respondents were nurses, with a frequency of 66, or 66 percent; medical labs, with a frequency of 11, or 11 percent; nursing aides, with a frequency of 8, or 8 percent; medical doctors, with a frequency of 7, or 7 percent; and midwives, dentists, pharmacists, and radiologists, with a frequency of 2, or 2 percent. This reflects that nurses comprise a significant number of professionals

in hospitals because they are the ones who give direct care to patients in every ward or unit of the hospital.

Number of years in service. Most respondents were in the service for five years and above, with a frequency of 40, or 40 percent; below one year, with a frequency of 24, or 24 percent; 1-2 years, with a frequency of 19, or 19 percent; and 3–4 years, with a frequency of 17, or 17 percent. This reflects that the respondents were employed in hospitals for extended periods.

Area of assignment. It can be gleaned that most of the respondents were in the outpatient department/emergency room, with a frequency of 38, or 38 percent; medical ward, with a frequency of 19, or 19 percent; laboratory, with a frequency of 9, or 9 percent; operating room, with a frequency of 8, or 8 percent, surgical/OB ward, with a frequency of 7, or 7 percent; Intensive Care Unit, with a frequency of 6, or 6 percent, and DR/Ward/Pharmacy, with a frequency of 2, or 2 percent. It reflects that more respondents were taken in the ER/OPD since it is the usual area where it is more convenient to see nurses in hospitals.

Employment status. According to the survey, the majority of participants were regular in their work, with a frequency of 53 or 53 percent; casual, with a frequency of 19 or 19 percent; contractual, with a frequency of 15 or 15 percent; and job order, with a frequency of 13 or 13 percent. This indicates that the respondents were already permanent in their positions. It is a fact that in hospitals, more employees are permanent in their positions.

Type of Facility. It showed that most respondents were employed in a government hospital, with a frequency of 58, or 58 percent, and those in private hospitals, with a frequency of 42, or 42 percent. This reflects that most respondents were employed in government hospitals. According to observations, there are more employees in government hospitals than in private hospitals, depending on the classification level.

Part II. Preventive Practices Performed by HealthCare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections

The preventive practices performed by healthcare workers to control nosocomial infection were discussed in tables 2 to 8, measuring personal hand hygiene and personal protective equipment; environmental; hospital ventilation; sterilization equipment and patient's area; water sanitation and waste segregation.

Table 2

**Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections
along Personal Hand Hygiene
n=100**

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I do palm to palm, right palm over the left dorsum and vice versa, palm to palm with fingers interlaced, backs of fingers to opposing palms, rubbing of thumbs and fingertips.	4.73	HP
2. I rinse my hands and wrists making sure all soap has been successfully washed off	4.82	HP
3. I always have in my pocket alcohol or hand sanitizer for my protection	4.35	P
4. I do hand hygiene before and after performing a clean or aseptic procedure	4.87	HP
5. I wash my hands after an exposure risk to bodily fluids and glove removal	4.93	HP
6. I do hand hygiene after contact with a patient and his immediate surrounding	4.89	HP
7. I perform hand hygiene after touching an inanimate object in the patient's immediate surroundings even if no direct patient contact	4.79	HP
8. I used alcohol-based hand sanitizers for hand hygiene when hands are not visibly soiled	4.71	HP
9. I ensure all surfaces on my both hands get covered with soap and I let it dry completely	4.77	HP
10. I wash for at least 15 to 20 seconds in a vigorous motion to cause friction making sure to include all surfaces of the hands and fingers	4.70	HP
AWM	4.76	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Personal Protective Employment

Table 3

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Personal Protective Employment

n=100

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I properly remove and dispose used contaminated PPE to prevent exposing myself and other people to infection.	4.88	HP
2. I protect the patient from injury or the spread of infection or illness by wearing the PPE	4.80	HP
3. I use gowns, mask and gloves to block transmission of contaminants from blood, body fluids, or respiratory secretions	4.86	HP
4. I protect patients who are at high risk for contracting infections through a surgical procedure or who have a medical condition, from being exposed to substances or potentially infectious material brought in by visitors and healthcare workers.	4.80	HP
5. I help protect myself from contamination and to prevent the spread of pathogens to subsequent patients by using gowns and masks	4.83	HP
6. I use gowns, eye goggles, gloves and gowns to prevent highly infectious diseases due to exposure to contaminated body fluids	4.78	HP
7. I practice respiratory/cough etiquette to prevent droplet transmission of respiratory pathogens using masks	4.85	HP
8. I use gloves to prevent contact with patient discharges as part of day-to-day duty	4.87	HP
9. I properly dispose used PPE every after duty in designated waste hamper	4.84	HP

10. I used eye goggles and an N-95 mask or higher-level respirator for airborne precautions	4.63	HP
AWM	4.81	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

The lowest indicator is item number 3, "I always have in my pocket alcohol or hand sanitizer for my protection," with a weighted mean of 4.35, or "Practiced." It showed that healthcare professionals were aware that alcohol or sanitizers are good ways of preventing the transmission of infection, and they usually have them with them every time they go on their duties. More often than not, hospitals have adequate supplies used by healthcare professionals to clean or sterilize equipment for patients.

Overall, the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along with Personal Hand Hygiene got an average weighted mean of 4.76, or "Highly Practiced." This connotes that healthcare professionals highly utilize hand hygiene because it eliminates germs in their patient care.

Correspondingly, Table 3 revealed the preventive practices of healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections along with Personal Protective Equipment. As gathered from the table, most indicators were rated "Highly Practiced," however, the highest indicators are item numbers 1, 3, and 8, "I properly remove and dispose of used contaminated PPE to prevent exposing myself and other people to infection," and "I use gowns, mask, and gloves to block transmission of contaminants from blood, body fluids, or respiratory secretions," and "I use gloves to prevent contact with patient discharges as part of day-to-day duty," with a weighted mean of 4.86, 4.87, and 4.89, or "Highly Practiced." As cited by the FDA (202), PPE acts as a barrier that potentially blocks the transmission of contaminants from blood, body fluids, or respiratory secretions. PPE protects patients at high risk of contracting infections through a surgical procedure or who have a medical condition from exposure to substances or potentially infectious material.

The lowest indicator is item 10, "I used eye goggles and an N-95 mask or higher-level respirator for airborne precautions," with a weighted mean of 4.63, or "Highly Practiced." It showed that the healthcare workers used different types of PPE to be safe from infection. Disposable masks should be thrown away once they are worn. According to the CDC (2023), N95s provide the most protection. KN95s and medical masks offer the next highest level of security. Cloth masks provide less protection, and surgical N95 masks are merely recommended for medical personnel.

Overall, the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Personal Protective Equipment got an average weighted mean of 4.81, or "Highly Practiced." It connotes that healthcare professionals highly regard the use of PPE in their clinical duty as their protection because they deal with patients with different illnesses. PPEs are worn to minimize exposure to hazards that cause serious workplace injuries and illnesses.

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Environmental (Hospital Ventilation)

Moreover, concerning the hospital ventilation, see Table 4. As derived from the table, the highest indicator is item number 2, "The room is cleaned regularly to eliminate foul odor and patient waste materials," with a weighted mean of 4.76, or "Highly Practiced." It reflects that a clean room will help patients recover early from their illnesses since poor ventilation in hospitals is detrimental to patients and others. According to Hudson (2018), appropriate ventilation rates are effective if applied correctly. Air device selection and placement, a clean source or outside air free of contaminants, the removal of pollutants through proper filtration or direct exhaust, and adequate controls capable of maintaining appropriate airflows and pressure relationships ensure that ventilation rates are effective in preventing infection within the hospital environment and ensuring the safety of patients and the public.

Table 4

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Environmental (Hospital Ventilation)

n=100

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I open the windows to improve the air quality and reduces the risk of germs spreading in the room	4.55	HP
2. The room is cleaned regularly to eliminate bad odors and patient waste materials	4.76	HP
3. Curtains of the patients room are changed regularly to remove dust and pathogens attached to it	4.53	HP
4. proper ventilation and indoor air quality is maintained to ensure proper infection control and patient safety.	4.62	HP

5. proper maintenance of electric fans and airconditioning units in the wards or private rooms	4.36	P
AWM	4.56	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

The lowest indicator is item 5, "proper maintenance of electric fans and air conditioning units in the wards or private rooms," with a weighted mean of 4.36, or "Practiced." It showed that the hospital's maintenance personnel did their jobs in maintaining the functionality of their equipment. The most important maintenance procedure to guarantee your air conditioner's effectiveness is to regularly clean or replace its filters. According to Energy.gov. (n.d.). "Clogged and unclean filters significantly decrease the effectiveness of a system because they restrict airflow. The most important maintenance procedure to guarantee an air conditioner's efficiency is regularly cleaning or replacing it. Clogged, dirty filters reduce the amount of airflow and significantly reduce a system's efficiency.

Overall, the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Personal Protective Equipment got an average weighted mean of 4.56, or "Highly Practiced." It connotes that the healthcare workers were very aware of the use of PPEs in the prevention of hospital-acquired infections. During the COVID-19 surge, everyone feared for their lives because they might get the virus, and most people used protective devices. People were curious about using protective devices to avoid transmission of the disease.

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Environmental (Water Sanitation)

Table 5 presents the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections and water sanitation.

As gleaned from the table, the highest indicator is item number 2, "I follow the guidelines in improving water management to reduce risks of waterborne infectious diseases," with a weighted mean of 4.62, or "Highly Practiced." It implied that the hospitals had a functional water systems. As the Centers for Disease Control mentioned, waterborne pathogen growth and spread can be reduced by implementing corrective measures and identifying dangerous conditions through the use of a healthcare water management program. Water harbors germs that threaten the safety of patients and

spread antibiotic-resistant pathogens or healthcare-associated infections (HAIs). Water management programs in healthcare facilities are an essential way to help protect vulnerable patient populations, staff, and visitors.

Table 5

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Environmental (Water Sanitation)

n=100

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I used in the ward water disinfection and sanitation treatment which can reduce viruses	4.53	HP
2. I follow the guidelines in improving water management to reduce risks of water-borne infectious diseases	4.62	HP
3. water management are used in the hospital that effectively lowers the rates of diseases spread by insects	4.49	P
4. The hospital had invested in safe drinking water with its water resource management system	4.59	HP
5. The rooms are equipped with continuous water supply	4.60	HP
AWM	4.57	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

The lowest indicator is item 3, "Water management is used in the hospital that effectively lowers the rates of diseases spread by insects," with a weighted mean of 4.49, or "Practiced." It showed that the hospitals ensured that the water system was safe for patients and other personnel. The primary concern of the hospital administration is to

maintain the quality of water in the hospitals to prevent the occurrence of pathogenic infections that affect patients and personnel.

Overall, the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections and Water Sanitation got an average weighted mean of 4.57, or "Highly Practiced." This connotes that the hospital observes the proper techniques to ensure a safe water supply. As the Centers for Disease Control mentions, water is the foundation of life; because of that, wet environments pose a particular hazard of infection, promoting microbial growth and serving as a source for antibiotic-resistant pathogens and healthcare-associated infections.

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Environmental (Sterilization of Equipment)

Table 6 presents the preventive practices of healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections and sterilize equipment. As a result, all the indicators were rated "Highly Practiced," however, the highest indicators are item numbers 2 and 3, "sterilization of equipment is done before and after any surgical procedure which destroys all microorganisms on the surface of an instrument," and "used instruments are cleaned using water with detergents or enzymatic cleaners before sterilizing or autoclaving," with a weighted mean of 4.85 and 4.86, or "Highly Practiced." It reflects that the hospitals properly disinfect their equipment to kill microbes that cause diseases. According to the Centers for Disease Control, sterilization destroys all microorganisms on the surface of an article or in a fluid to prevent disease transmission associated with using that item. Most medical and surgical devices used in healthcare facilities are made of heat-stable materials and undergo heat, primarily steam sterilization.

The lowest indicator is item number 4, "I clean and wrap instruments, load the sterilizer, operate the sterilizer, and monitor the entire process," with a weighted mean of 4.75, or "Highly Practiced." It showed that the respondents knew very well that instruments used in patient care must be cleaned after use and have to be sterilized using a disinfectant or an autoclave for high sterilization. Every unit of the hospital has its way of making its equipment clean and suitable for patient use. Infections can happen when equipment is not properly cared for.

Table 6

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Environmental (Sterilization of Equipment)

n=100

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Appropriate disinfection and sterilization of supplies and equipment is done which can help prevent healthcare-associated infections.	4.78	HP
2. sterilization of equipment is done before and after any surgical procedure which destroys all microorganisms on the surface of an instrument	4.86	HP
3. used instruments are cleaned using water with detergents or enzymatic cleaners before sterilizing or autoclaving	4.85	HP
4. I clean and wrap instruments, load the sterilizer, operate the sterilizer, and monitor of the entire process.	4.75	HP
5. surgical instruments are sterilized and wrapped in the central supply prior to use to protect patients from infections	4.79	HP
A W M	4.81	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

Overall, the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections, along with sterilization of equipment, got an average weighted mean of 4.81, or “Highly Practiced.” This connotes that the respondents are utilizing properly sterilized equipment for the protection of patients. Crucial medical devices come into touch with

sterile bodily fluids or tissues. These objects should only be used sterilized because microbiological contamination can spread illness.

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Environmental (Waste Segregation)

The preventive practices used by healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections are displayed in Table 7 along with waste segregation.

Table 7

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along Environmental (Waste Segregation)

n=100

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I practice proper waste segregation and proper handling of healthcare wastes	4.85	HP
2. Waste are segregated in different trash bins depending on the waste materials	4.82	HP
3. Trash bins are provided with covers to prevent entry of flies	4.80	HP
4. Trash bins are collected regularly for proper disposal by the utility worker	4.78	HP
5. I optimize the placement of collection containers to ensure they are easily accessible	4.82	HP
AWM	4.81	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

As gleaned from the table, all the indicators were rated “Highly Practiced,” however, the highest indicators are item number 1, “I practice proper waste segregation and proper handling of healthcare wastes,” with a weighted mean of 4.85, or “Highly Practiced.” Every healthcare worker is expected to know the proper segregation of waste since there are many types of waste in hospitals. Color-coded trash bins are provided in hospitals depending on the waste materials.

According to Karpinska et al. 2023, hazardous waste is a particular type of waste which, if not adequately treated and segregated, can pose a risk to human health and the environment. HCW (healthcare waste) contains potentially harmful microorganisms that can be spread among healthcare personnel, hospital patients, and the general public, causing severe illnesses. Healthcare personnel are the specialists especially exposed to this risk.

The lowest indicator is item number 4, “Trash bins are collected regularly for proper disposal by the utility worker,” with a weighted mean of 4.78 or “Highly Practiced.” It showed that hospital wastes are appropriately segregated and disposed of regularly because these are causes of infection since flies and other insects harbor them if not regularly disposed of. This area is also part of those monitored by monitoring teams in hospitals like the Department of Health and other agencies. Trash bins are segregated depending on the type of trash.

Overall, the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections along waste segregation got an average weighted mean of 4.81, or “Highly Practiced.” It connotes that the healthcare workers practiced proper waste segregation for different types of waste. Also, according to Karpinska et al. 2023, If medical waste is placed in a landfill for disposal without being processed and separated, chemicals, medications, or dangerous microbes may find their way into the soil and groundwater, contaminating it.

Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections

Healthcare Workers' Preventive Measures to Reduce Nosocomial Infections are shown in Table 8.

All aspects of healthcare workers' preventive practices were rated as "Highly Practiced," as can be seen from the table. However, hand hygiene and the use of personal protective equipment received the highest rating on the individual element, with an average weighted mean of 4.79, or "Highly Practiced." Practicing hand hygiene is the most practical and cost-effective way to guard against the spread of nosocomial infections. Because healthcare personnel frequently come into contact with patients, their hands can quickly become infected with bacteria and viruses.

Table 8**Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections
n=100**

Aspect	WM	DE
Personal		
Hand Hygiene	4.76	HP
Personal Protective Equipment	4.81	HP
	AWM 4.79	HP
Environmental		
Hospital Ventilation	4.56	HP
Water Sanitation	4.57	HP
Sterilization of Equipment	4.81	HP
Waste Segregation	4.81	HP
	AWM 4.69	HP
	OWM 4.74	HP

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4.50 – 5.00	Highly Practiced (HP)
3.50 – 4.49	Practiced (P)
2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Practiced (MP)
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Practiced (SP)
1.00 – 1.49	Not Practiced (NP)

The lowest aspect is environmental, which includes hospital ventilation, water sanitation, sterilization of equipment, and waste segregation, with an average weighted mean of 4.69, or “Highly Practiced.” This showed that the healthcare workers were aware of these practices and performed them in the clinical area to safeguard themselves and other hospital personnel. Trash bins are provided in every room and station to contain the microbes in the discharges and other fomites in the patients' rooms.

Overall, the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections got an average weighted mean of 4.74, or “Highly Practiced.” It connotes that healthcare workers highly utilize different practices to prevent nosocomial infections. Healthcare employees were trained to do the practices to safeguard their patients against disease transmission.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Age

Table 9 presents the test results of differences in the preventive practices of healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections across ages.

All the computed F-values in the considered aspects reveal significance values higher than the set .05 level of significance. This leads to the acceptance of the theory stating there doesn't seem a substantial variation in healthcare workers' personal and environmental preventive practices to control nosocomial infections. This means that young and old healthcare workers provide the same level of training in both individual and ecological aspects. It only showed that all healthcare workers were practicing the different elements to limit, if not eliminate, the causes of nosocomial infections. Every healthcare worker's primary duty is to safeguard the patients while admitted to the hospital.

Table 9

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Age

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Hand Hygiene	Between Groups	.081	3	.027	.233	.873	Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.125	96	.116			
	Total	11.206	99				
Personal Protective Equipment	Between Groups	.214	3	.071	.590	.623	Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.626	96	.121			
	Total	11.840	99				
Overall-Personal	Between Groups	.127	3	.042	.412	.745	Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.890	96	.103			
	Total	10.018	99				
Hospital Ventilation	Between Groups	1.119	3	.373	1.292	.282	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.712	96	.289			
	Total						

	Total	28.830	99				
Water Sanitation	Between Groups	1.658	3	.553			
	Within Groups	27.547	96	.287	1.926	.131	Not Significant
	Total	29.204	99				
Sterilization of Equipment	Between Groups	.210	3	.070			
	Within Groups	17.747	96	.185	.378	.769	Not Significant
	Total	17.956	99				
Waste Segregation	Between Groups	.275	3	.092			
	Within Groups	15.745	96	.164	.560	.643	Not Significant
	Total	16.020	99				
Overall-Environmental	Between Groups	.448	3	.149			
	Within Groups	14.924	96	.155	.960	.415	Not Significant
	Total	15.372	99				

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Gender Preference

Table 10 presents the difference in the preventive practices of healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections across gender preference.

Table 10

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Gender Preference

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Hand Hygiene	Between Groups	1.471	2	.735			
	Within Groups	9.736	97	.100	7.327	.001	Significant
	Total	11.206	99				

Personal Protective Equipment	Between Groups	1.099	2	.549	4.961	.009	Significant
	Within Groups	10.742	97	.111			
	Total	11.840	99				
Overall-Personal	Between Groups	1.255	2	.627	6.945	.002	Significant
	Within Groups	8.763	97	.090			
	Total	10.018	99				
Hospital Ventilation	Between Groups	1.534	2	.767	2.726	.071	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.296	97	.281			
	Total	28.830	99				
Water Sanitation	Between Groups	.399	2	.200	.672	.513	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.805	97	.297			
	Total	29.204	99				
Sterilization of Equipment	Between Groups	.220	2	.110	.601	.550	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.737	97	.183			
	Total	17.956	99				
Waste Segregation	Between Groups	.751	2	.375	2.385	.097	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.269	97	.157			
	Total	16.020	99				
Overall-Environmental	Between Groups	.613	2	.306	2.013	.139	Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.759	97	.152			
	Total	15.372	99				

Based on the computed F-values, which generated significance values lower than the set .05 level of significance along personal aspects, both hand hygiene and personal protective equipment, the rejection of the null hypothesis is apparent. This implies that the gender preference of the health workers affects their personal preventive practices to

control nosocomial infections. More detailed statistical data on groups showing significant differences in personal preventive practices across gender preferences is shown in Table 11.

Meanwhile, the computed F-values along the environmental aspect provided significance values higher than the set .05 significance level. As a result, the null hypothesis will be accepted. Hence, gender preference does not affect the environmental preventive practices of healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections.

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Gender Preference

Table 11 illustrates how healthcare personnel' environmental preventive strategies varies significantly depending on gender preferences when it comes to controlling nosocomial infections.

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Gender Preference

Table 11

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Gender Preference

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
Hand Hygiene	Man vs Woman	-.217	.007
Personal Protective Equipment	Man vs Woman	-.213	.013
Overall-Personal	Man vs Woman	-.215	.005

It is evident in the table that significant differences exist between men and women regarding personal preventive practices. The significant negative mean difference implies that women have a higher level of training than men in terms of personal preventive practices of health workers to control nosocomial infections. It means that women healthcare workers are more meticulous in rendering their nursing care than males. We know the background of females since they often do chores at home, so they are more used to working for their families.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Civil Status

Table 12 exhibits the variations in nosocomial infection control measures used by healthcare professionals based on their civil status.

Table 12

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Civil Status

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Hand Hygiene	Between Groups	.128	2	.064	.561	.573	Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.078	97	.114			
	Total	11.206	99				
Personal Protective Equipment	Between Groups	.204	2	.102	.851	.430	Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.636	97	.120			
	Total	11.840	99				
Overall-Personal	Between Groups	.144	2	.072	.709	.495	Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.873	97	.102			
	Total	10.018	99				
Hospital Ventilation	Between Groups	.041	2	.020	.069	.934	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.790	97	.297			
	Total	28.830	99				
Water Sanitation	Between Groups	.131	2	.065	.218	.804	Not Significant
	Within Groups	29.074	97	.300			
	Total	29.204	99				
Sterilization of Equipment	Between Groups	.051	2	.025	.138	.871	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.906	97	.185			
	Total	17.956	99				
Waste Segregation	Between Groups	.069	2	.035	.211	.810	Not Significant
	Within Groups						

	Within Groups	15.951	97	.164			
	Total	16.020	99				
Overall- Environmental	Between Groups	.012	2	.006	.039	.961	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.359	97	.158			
	Total	15.372	99				

The computed F-values provided significance values which are higher than the set .05 level of significance. This suggests that the results are not significant. Therefore, the civil status of the health workers does not affect their preventive health practices to control nosocomial infections. It goes to show that their civil status has no direct effect and their practices in preventing nosocomial infections.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Highest Educational Attainment

Table 13

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Highest Educational Attainment

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Hand Hygiene	Between Groups	.274	3	.091	.803	.495	Not Significant
	Within Groups	10.932	96	.114			
	Total	11.206	99				
Personal Protective Equipment	Between Groups	.233	3	.078	.641	.590	Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.608	96	.121			
	Total	11.840	99				
Overall-Personal	Between Groups	.226	3	.075	.738	.532	Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.792	96	.102			
	Total	10.018	99				
Hospital Ventilation	Between Groups	1.727	3	.576	2.039	.114	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.103	96	.282			
	Total	28.830	99				

Water Sanitation	Between Groups	1.079	3	.360	1.227	.304	Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.126	96	.293			
	Total	29.204	99				
Sterilization of Equipment	Between Groups	.173	3	.058	.311	.817	Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.783	96	.185			
	Total	17.956	99				
Waste Segregation	Between Groups	.254	3	.085	.514	.673	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.767	96	.164			
	Total	16.020	99				
Overall-Environmental	Between Groups	.437	3	.146	.935	.427	Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.935	96	.156			
	Total	15.372	99				

The differences in healthcare professionals' preventive measures to reduce nosocomial infections across the highest educational attainment levels are shown in Table 13.

The computed F-values along personal and environmental aspects indicated significance values higher than the set .05 significance level. Data suggest that the educational attainment of health workers does not affect their preventive practices to control nosocomial infections. It goes to show that the respondents had comparable preventive practices in the control of infections. It only implies that they were focused on their jobs and did not like that their patients would acquire the infection while confined in the hospital.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Professional Area

The variations in the preventive methods used by healthcare professionals across professional areas to reduce nosocomial infections are shown in Table 14.

Table 14

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Professional Area

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Hand Hygiene	Between Groups	.665	7	.095	.829	.566	Not Significant
	Within Groups	10.541	92	.115			
	Total	11.206	99				
Personal Protective Equipment	Between Groups	.960	7	.137	1.159	.334	Not Significant
	Within Groups	10.880	92	.118			
	Total	11.840	99				
Overall-Personal	Between Groups	.772	7	.110	1.097	.372	Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.246	92	.100			
	Total	10.018	99				
Hospital Ventilation	Between Groups	1.441	7	.206	.691	.679	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.390	92	.298			
	Total	28.830	99				
Water Sanitation	Between Groups	3.195	7	.456	1.615	.141	Not Significant
	Within Groups	26.009	92	.283			
	Total	29.204	99				
Sterilization of Equipment	Between Groups	1.530	7	.219	1.224	.298	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.426	92	.179			
	Total	17.956	99				
Waste Segregation	Between Groups	.334	7	.048	.280	.960	Not Significant
	Within Groups						

	Within Groups	15.687	92	.171			
	Total	16.020	99				
Overall- Environmental	Between Groups	.729	7	.104			Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.643	92	.159	.654	.710	
	Total	15.372	99				

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Number of Years in Service

Table 15 displays how healthcare professionals' preventive measures for preventing nosocomial infections vary depending on how long they have worked there.

Table 15

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Number of Years in Service

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Hand Hygiene	Between Groups	.238	3	.079			Not Significant
	Within Groups	10.968	96	.114	.695	.557	
	Total	11.206	99				
Personal Protective Equipment	Between Groups	.353	3	.118			Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.488	96	.120	.983	.404	
	Total	11.840	99				
Overall- Personal	Between Groups	.241	3	.080			Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.776	96	.102	.790	.502	
	Total	10.018	99				
Hospital Ventilation	Between Groups	.691	3	.230	.786	.505	Not Significant

	Within Groups	28.139	96	.293			
	Total	28.830	99				
Water Sanitation	Between Groups	.385	3	.128			Not Significant
	Within Groups	28.819	96	.300	.428	.734	
	Total	29.204	99				
Sterilization of Equipment	Between Groups	.726	3	.242			Not Significant
	Within Groups	17.231	96	.179	1.347	.264	
	Total	17.956	99				
Waste Segregation	Between Groups	.388	3	.129			Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.632	96	.163	.795	.500	
	Total	16.020	99				
Overall- Environmental	Between Groups	.399	3	.133			Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.973	96	.156	.853	.468	
	Total	15.372	99				

Computed F-values, which generated sig values that are higher than the set .05 level of significance, indicate insignificant results. This means that the number of years in service of the healthcare workers does not affect their preventive practices to control nosocomial infections. It revealed that the respondents perform their preventive practices regardless of their years in the service. The respondents do the daily routine in the area, so they are used to doing it in the best interest of their patients so as not to incur nosocomial infections.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Area of Assignment

The differences in the preventive measures utilized by healthcare professionals to avoid nosocomial infections by assignment area are shown in Table 16.

Table 16

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Area of Assignment

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Hand Hygiene	Between Groups	2.980	9	.331	3.623	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	8.226	90	.091			
	Total	11.206	99				
Personal Protective Equipment	Between Groups	3.026	9	.336	3.433	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	8.815	90	.098			
	Total	11.840	99				
Overall-Personal	Between Groups	2.834	9	.315	3.945	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	7.183	90	.080			
	Total	10.018	99				
Hospital Ventilation	Between Groups	2.071	9	.230	.774	.641	Not Significant
	Within Groups	26.759	90	.297			
	Total	28.830	99				
Water Sanitation	Between Groups	4.825	9	.536	1.979	.051	Not Significant
	Within Groups	24.380	90	.271			
	Total	29.204	99				
Sterilization of Equipment	Between Groups	2.204	9	.245	1.399	.200	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.752	90	.175			
	Total	17.956	99				
Waste Segregation	Between Groups	1.883	9	.209	1.332	.232	Not Significant
	Within Groups						

	Within Groups	14.138	90	.157			
	Total	16.020	99				
Overall- Environmental	Between Groups	1.573	9	.175			
	Within Groups	13.798	90	.153	1.140	.343	Not Significant
	Total	15.372	99				

Table 16 displays the difference in the preventive practices of healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections across area of assignment. Results indicate that personal preventive practices to control nosocomial infections are significantly different across area of assignment. This implies that the area of assignment of the health workers significantly affects their personal preventive practices to control nosocomial infections. Table 17 on the next page shows a more comprehensive set of data on this significant difference.

On the other hand, no significant difference exists along environmental preventive practices to control nosocomial infections across area of assignment. This indicates that the area of assignment of health workers does not affect the environmental preventive practices to control nosocomial infections. It revealed that the respondents regardless of their area of assignment perform their activities to safeguard the patients from acquiring nosocomial infections while they are recovering in the hospital.

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Area of Assignment

The Scheffe Test results for the significant differences in healthcare professionals' personal preventative actions to control nosocomial infections across areas of assignment are shown in Table 17.

Table 17

Scheffe Test Results on the Significant Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Area of Assignment

Aspect	Compared Groups	Mean Difference	Sig
	OPD/ER vs DR	1.000	.022
	Medical vs DR	1.121	.007
Hand	OB vs DR	1.186	.009
Hygiene	ICU vs DR	1.200	.010
	OR vs DR	1.175	.008
	Lab vs DR	1.089	.019

The table shows that the rest of the assignment areas are compared with the delivery room area. The significant positive mean differences indicate that the healthcare workers assigned in the DR have provided lower ratings on their level of personal preventive practices than those assigned in the OPD/ER, medical, OB, OR, ICU, and laboratory. This implies that those designated in the DR are rated lower than those in the other areas. However, those healthcare workers still perform their duties to prevent nosocomial infection among their patients. A low rating was given.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Employment Status

Table 18 reveals the difference in the preventive practices of healthcare workers in controlling nosocomial infections across employment statuses.

The results are not significant, as evidenced in the computed F-values with corresponding significance values, which are higher than the set .05 level of significance. This means that the healthcare workers' employment status is the same regarding personal and environmental preventive practices to control nosocomial infections. It implies that regardless of their positions and employment standing, healthcare workers do what is necessary to maintain their duty to prevent the incidence of nosocomial infections. The ultimate goal of employees in a hospital is for better patient care outcomes and early recovery among patients.

Table 18

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Employment Status

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Hand Hygiene	Between Groups	.115	3	.038	.332	.802	Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.091	96	.116			
	Total	11.206	99				
Personal Protective Equipment	Between Groups	.475	3	.158	1.337	.267	Not Significant
	Within Groups	11.366	96	.118			
	Total	11.840	99				
Overall-Personal	Between Groups	.184	3	.061	.599	.617	Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.833	96	.102			

		Total	10.018	99				
Hospital Ventilation	Between		1.062	3	.354			
	Groups							
	Within		27.768	96	.289	1.224	.305	Not Significant
		Total	28.830	99				
Water Sanitation	Between		.147	3	.049			
	Groups							
	Within		29.057	96	.303	.162	.921	Not Significant
		Total	29.204	99				
Sterilization of Equipment	Between		.340	3	.113			
	Groups							
	Within		17.616	96	.184	.618	.605	Not Significant
		Total	17.956	99				
Waste Segregation	Between		.158	3	.053			
	Groups							
	Within		15.862	96	.165	.319	.812	Not Significant
		Total	16.020	99				
Overall-Environmental	Between		.241	3	.080			
	Groups							
	Within		15.130	96	.158	.511	.676	Not Significant
		Total	15.372	99				

t-Test Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Type of Facility

The differences in healthcare personnel's preventive measures to manage nosocomial infections by type of facility are shown in Table 19.

Table 19

t-Test Results on the Difference in the Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections across Type of Facility

Aspect	Type of Facility	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	Df	t-value	Significance	Remarks
Hand Hygiene	Private	4	4.80	.068	.068	9	.992	.323	Not Significant
	Government	5	4.73						
PPE	Private	4	4.88	.120	.069	9	1.723	.088	Not Significant
	Government	5	4.76						
Overall-Personal	Private	4	4.84	.094	.064	9	1.461	.147	Not Significant
	Government	5	4.75						
Hospital Ventilation	Private	4	4.70	.234	.107	9	2.185	.031	Not Significant
	Government	5	4.47						
Water Sanitation	Private	4	4.60	.050	.110	9	.456	.649	Not Significant
	Government	5	4.54						
Sterilization of Equipment	Private	4	4.85	.072	.086	9	.830	.088	Not Significant
	Government	5	4.78						
Waste Segregation	Private	4	4.83	.025	.082	9	.307	.760	Not Significant
	Government	5	4.80						

Overall- Environmental	Private	4 2	4.74	.095	.080	9 8	1.19 8	.2 3 4	Not Significant
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The computed t-values provided significance values higher than the set .05 significance level. The results indicate no significant difference exists in the health workers' personal and environmental preventive practices when grouped according to the affiliated facility type. This further means that healthcare workers who work in private and government facilities share the same personal and environmental preventive practices to control nosocomial infections. It revealed whether a patient is admitted in public or private and enjoys the care given by the healthcare workers since the primary goal of their employment in a hospital is to help patients attain satisfaction with the services.

Relationship Between the Personal Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections and their Profile Variables

Table 20 shows the relationship between the personal preventive practices of healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections and their profile variables.

Significant positive R-values are evident between personal preventive practices and gender. The positive R-values indicate a direct relationship. This means gender preference is significantly related to the personal preventive practices of healthcare workers.

Meanwhile, no significant relationship exists between the personnel preventive practices of healthcare workers and the other profile variables. This implies that healthcare workers should implement preventive measures to prevent their patients from getting infected while confined in the hospital.

Table 20

Relationship Between the Personal Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections and their Profile Variables

Profile Variable	Hand Hygiene		Personal Protective Equipment		Overall Personal Practices	
	r-value	Sig	r-value	sig	r-value	Sig
Age	.025	.803	.106	.293	.071	.482
Gender Preference	.211*	.035	.238*	.017	.241*	.016

Civil Status	.104	.305	.118	.243	.119	.239
Highest Educational Attainment	-.004	.965	.079	.434	.041	.688
Professional Area	-.062	.539	-.151	.135	-.115	.255
Number of Years in Service	-.108	.285	-.146	.146	-.137	.175
Area of Assignment	.068	.502	-.012	.907	.029	.771
Employment Status	-.013	.898	.116	.252	.056	.580
Type of Facility	-.100	.323	-.171	.088	-.146	.147

*Significant at .05 level

Relationship Between the Environmental Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections and their Profile Variables

Table 21 presents the relationship between the environmental preventive practices of healthcare workers to control nosocomial infections and their profile variables.

As shown in the results, a significant negative R-value is evident between hospital ventilation and the type of facility.

Healthcare workers have become more affiliated with private facilities as they adhere to environmental preventive practices, specifically hospital ventilation. The study revealed that private institutions were more equipped with patient care facilities than government facilities. Private hospitals often upgrade their facilities to improve their services and charge much higher than government facilities. In private hospitals, more patients' rooms are well-ventilated and airconditioned and provided with adequate utility

workers to maintain sanitation. No other significant relationships have been detected between environmental preventive practices and other profile variables.

Table 21

Relationship Between the Environmental Preventive Practices of Healthcare Workers to Control Nosocomial Infections and their Profile Variables

Profile Variable	Hospital Ventilation		Water Sanitation		Sterilization of Equipment		Waste Segregation		Overall – Environmental	
	r-value	Sig	r-value	Sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig		
Age	.041	.687	-.025	.807	.046	.652	.117	.247	.048	.638
Gender Preference	.087	.411	.084	.404	.102	.313	.130	.196	.161	.110
Civil Status	.003	.980	.007	.949	.032	.749	.065	.522	.028	.779
Highest Educational Attainment	.128	.205	.015	.884	.054	.597	.117	.247	.093	.357
Professional Area	-.060	.555	-.018	.858	-.050	.618	.114	.257	-.011	.913
Number of Years in Service	-.101	.319	-.093	.357	-.164	.103	-.144	.152	-.148	.143

Area of Assignment	-.016	.876	-.058	.565	-.009	.932	-.028	.780	-.035	.730
Employment Status	.182	.070	.034	.736	.128	.203	.037	.711	.118	.241
Type of Facility	-.216*	.031	-.046	.649	-.084	.408	-.031	.760	-.120	.234

*Significant at .05 level

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following are at this moment concluded:

The healthcare worker respondents were mainly young adults, women, singles, and bachelor's degree holders; most were nurses in the service for more than five years, primarily assigned to OPD/ER, regular employees, and mostly from government facilities. The preventive practices among healthcare workers are highest on personal hand hygiene and personal protective equipment and lowest on environmental. The gender preference of the health workers affects their preventive practices to control nosocomial infections, while environmental preventive practices do not affect the healthcare workers' ability to prevent nosocomial infections. Women healthcare workers are more meticulous in rendering their nursing care than men, and the area of assignment of the health workers significantly affects their preventive practices to control nosocomial infections. The health care workers perform preventive practices to keep their patients free from infection while they are confined in the hospital. Healthcare workers affiliated with private facilities adhere more to environmental preventive practices, specifically hospital ventilation. The proposed effective measures for preventing nosocomial infections are proposed for adaptation.

Recommendations

Based on the formulated conclusions, the following are at this moment offered:

Healthcare workers must continue to upgrade their qualifications for more updated knowledge and practices in preventing nosocomial infections.

The respondents must enhance their preventive practices to prevent nosocomial infections and environmental factors, including hospital ventilation and water quality.

Regardless of their gender preferences, healthcare workers must continue to practice the different aspects of preventing nosocomial infections.

Healthcare workers must improve their environmental practices so that their personal and environmental aspects are on par.

Since healthcare workers' hands are the most prevalent means of spreading healthcare-associated microorganisms from patient to patient and throughout the healthcare environment, hand cleanliness can help avoid many healthcare-associated infections. Here are the essential infection management techniques to lessen the spread of diseases. Staff Education is continuous. The key to effective infection control is having a well-trained staff member; without them, infection control measures would not be practical, routine audits would not be conducted, and transparent policies and procedures would not be established.

The health care workers render preventive measures to keep their patients free from infection while confined in the hospital. Healthcare workers affiliated with private facilities adhere more to environmental preventive practices, specifically hospital ventilation. The recommended practical steps—sanitation of medical equipment, waste segregation, supply of sufficient personal protective equipment, sanitizers, antiseptics, hospital ventilation, hygienic surroundings, and hand hygiene—to lower the chance of infections related to medical care. The practices would be more effective if there were provisions for an adequate water supply in the different areas for hand hygiene and the availability of personal preventive equipment among health professionals to prevent nosocomial infections.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher diligently ensured adherence to ethical precautions and procedures throughout the study. Every step of the research process was guided by careful consideration of moral principles, including:

Respect for Participant Autonomy:

Prioritizing informed consent ensures participants understand the study's objectives, potential risks, and benefits before obtaining their consent, ensuring their agreement is voluntary and free from pressure or coercion.

Confidentiality and Privacy Protection:

Safeguarding participant data and implementing strict measures to protect the confidentiality and privacy of participant's personal information and research data, ensuring that only authorized personnel can access them.

Beneficence and non-maleficence:

Minimizing harm, taking necessary precautions to mitigate potential risks or damage to participants during the research process, and ensuring their well-being is always prioritized.

Transparency and Disclosure:

Providing clear information and maintaining transparency in all aspects of the research, including the research objectives, methodology, and potential conflicts of interest, ensuring that participants are fully informed.

Fair Treatment and Equity:

Ensuring fairness that all participants are treated fairly and equitably, regardless of age, gender, race, ethnicity, or socioeconomic status, and that their contributions are valued equally.

Professional Integrity:

Upholding ethical standards, conducting the research with honesty, integrity, and objectivity, avoiding bias, fabrication, or falsification of data, and adhering to ethical guidelines and regulations.

Participant Advocacy:

Advocating for participants' rights and well-being throughout the research process, addressing any concerns or grievances they may have, and ensuring that their voices are heard and respected.

Conflict of Interest Management:

Managing conflicts during the research process involves disclosing any potential conflicts of interest and taking appropriate measures to manage them transparently and ethically.

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